

Quantum Resolution Entropy?

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The concept of thermodynamic entropy originates in classical physics, in particular in the first law which is related to energy distribution. For example, even though particle states are often defined through p and x , in many cases it is the p (or $pp/2m$) distribution which is key as in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas or collective kinetic energy converted to heat.

In quantum mechanics, defining a precise energy state, e.g. one associated with p momentum or j angular momentum, involves a second variable associated with a mathematical generator e.g. d/dx or $d/d\theta$. A high value of p or j suggests a sharp resolution function, i.e. high information in this second variable. Thus, we argue that there is a new type of entropy introduced, namely resolution entropy, which does not exist in classical physics. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ represents a classically sharp p and corresponding $pp/2m$, but there is uncertainty in x . The question we ask is whether there are any properties associated with this new entropy. We suggest that like in the classical case, a spontaneous change should lead to an increase in this new entropy even if in terms of energy it seems that one has usual dynamics with no entropic considerations. In particular, we apply this idea to a quantum bound state.

The Notion of Entropy

The notion of entropy comes historically from classical physics. It first appears in the three laws of thermodynamics and then in $-k \ln \Omega$ of the number of states in classical statistical mechanics. Classical states, however, are counted using variables such as p and x which are considered to be arbitrarily sharp. Furthermore, thermodynamical entropy, although associated with space, seems to be more focused on momentum or energy. For example, a body (collection of molecules) with translational motion converts some of this energy into heat. In other words, the entropy created is particularly associated with an energy distribution at a noncollective motion level. Similarly, $\exp(-e/T)$ is associated with collisions. Thus, thermodynamic entropy seems to be more than just the counting of states. It seems to be linked to interactions involving energy.

We argue that the classical notion of entropy seems to exist a priori and is then “fitted” into a quantum world, which may actually be different from the classical one.

Quantum Mechanics

A quantum free particle has a momentum p , a kinetic energy $pp/2m$ at each x and undergoes impulse hits in a classical manner. So far, there seems to be no notion of probability or entropy. The problem is that p is defined in terms of a mathematical generator d/dx acting on a function which plays the role of a kind of square root probability, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. It is possible that this generator represents a way of measuring the variable p .

In other words, one does not have sharp x , p points dynamically, but a distribution in x . This suggests a certain uncertainty in x . The larger p the sharper the humps of $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. the more the order or information. Losing p , or energy, means less resolution or sharpness, i.e. more

entropy one might suggest. This however, is a new kind of entropy, which we call resolution entropy, which does not exist classically. It has nothing to do with conservation of momentum linked impulse hits which are still classical, but is associated with spatial features of interactions, such as two slit interference, which also do not occur classically. As a result, one may have a quantum free particle change the magnitude of momentum such that $dE = d \text{Work}$, implying no entropy change, because there is no heat involved, but actually the new resolution entropy changes.

We ask: Is the resolution entropy linked to energy changes in a manner consistent with say the second law of thermodynamics?

Rules Associated with Resolution Entropy

$\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle, but impulse hits which change the magnitude of p seem to be classical and not linked with entropy. Nevertheless, there is a very specific p related distribution pattern, i.e. the slope of $\cos(px)$ is sharp for high p values, because $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$. This, in turn, defines a high resolution, or high information or order in space. As a result, a regular classical p or $pp/2m$, is now associated with order (lack of entropy). Removing energy removes resolution or order and so this is equivalent to an increase in resolution entropy, even though a free particle does not spontaneously shed energy, but undergoes classical-like impulse hits. Nevertheless, there is the idea that as the particle loses more and more energy, its spatial entropy increases, i.e. it loses resolution. Thus, one might suggest a general tendency for a particle to lose or shed energy. This is not particularly convincing at the free particle level, but becomes more so for a bound particle, we argue.

Quantum Bound Particle

A quantum bound particle is described by an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. wavefunction = \sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This in turn represents a periodic type of real function with varying heights and hump widths. A higher energy implies sharper resolution, just as in the free particle case. This in turn implies more order, resolution. In the bound case, one may have spontaneous decay as a photon or phonon etc may be emitted. It seems that for this new resolution entropy, an idea equivalent to the second law of thermodynamics holds, because there is a tendency for resolution (order) to be spontaneously lost as a photon is emitted and the particle drops to a lower energy, more spatially blurred state.

Thermodynamic Versus Resolution Entropy

In the literature it seems that there is one notion of entropy, usually given by Shannon's entropy - $k \sum$ over i $P(i) \ln(P(i))$. Thus, if a $P(i)$ (probability) appears, one may try to create a kind of entropy. This is done for a bound state using $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ ((1a)) and $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ ((1b)), while at the same time von Neumann entropy suggests zero entropy for a pure state. Furthermore, Maxwell-Boltzmann ideas seem to be applied to a system with a single particle jumping from one energy level to another by interacting with photons. This, we argue, follows from thermodynamic energy related entropy, while ((1a)) and ((1b)) are more related to the

resolution entropy, which seems to be a quantum concept not found in classical physics. Nevertheless, we have tried to argue that there is some physics associated with this resolution entropy as it is linked to spontaneous drops in energy. The question is whether there is a quantitative link or not with energy drop rates. Usual photon emission/absorption pictures assume no such link.

Various Kinds of Resolution Entropies

Resolution entropy is not just associated with spatial resolution in $\exp(ipx)$, but also with angular resolution in $\exp(-imx)$ where m is the z projection of angular momentum. Given that spin follows the same math as angular momentum, one might look for some spin entropy, but it does not seem to be linked to a variable such as x or θ .

Conclusion

In conclusion, thermodynamic entropy follows from classical physics and seems to be closely linked to energy interactions as shown by the first law of thermodynamics. Classical statistical mechanics allows for a calculation of thermodynamic entropy in terms of $P(e_i)$ for a classical gas, i.e. $-k \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$, but after this, any probability seems to be fair game for a Shannon's entropy calculation.

We argue that quantum mechanics differs from classical mechanics in that a precise classical value such as p , and hence $pp/2m$, follows from a measurement using a mathematical generator, e.g. d/dx . The larger p , the sharper the slope of the function of px . This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ and an uncertainty in x . The higher p , the more resolution or order, i.e. the less resolution entropy. Thus, we introduce a nonthermodynamic entropy linked with this resolution order. The loss of energy seems to coincide with less resolution or blurriness. A free particle does not spontaneously shed energy, but a bound one does and a bound state is based on a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s which create a periodic type function. It has high resolution for high energy, but may spontaneously shed a photon and become more blurred. Thus, the new spatial resolution seems to follow a kind of second law of thermodynamics.